

Single pine pellet gasification at 900 °C under CO₂ and H₂O atmospheres for biomass Chemical Looping Combustion applications

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1. Context of the study

Bio-CLC (Biomass-Chemical Looping Combustion)

- industrial conditions:
- high heating rates
 - centimeter-size biomass

AIM OF THE STUDY:

INFLUENCE OF BIOMASS TYPE ON CARBONACEOUS PRODUCTS FROM FAST PYROLYSIS AT 900 °C FOR BIO-CLC APPLICATIONS

2. Materials and methods

Drop tube furnace configurations
Biomass feedstock

2. Materials and methods

Biomass feedstock

Sample number	1	2	3	4	5	6
Sample name	1-pellet-p-eow	2-pellet-p	3-chip-p	4-chip-b	5-stick-p	6-stick-b
Shape of wood particles	Pellet (l = 1.5 cm, ϕ = 6 mm)*					
Wood species	Pine		Pine	Beech	Pine	Beech
Biomass per test	1		1	about 10	1	
P. density (kg/m ³)	1225			550 - 650		

distinctive features:

- shape
- density
- contact surface

* *l*, length
 ϕ , diameter
w, width
e, thickness

3. Experiments

Results: pyrolysis (100% N₂) and gasification (100% CO₂)

1. Experiments

Results: pyrolysis (100% N₂) and gasification (100% CO₂)

Modeling:

Mass and carbonaceous gas emissions (CO, CO₂, THC) ok

Work in progress: determining the reaction order for the relatively linear phase, and further investigation for the short phase that rapidly drops to zero at the end

2. Experiments

Influence of CO₂ concentration

Determination of the reaction order

Char samples (0.5 g < m < 0.7 g) were gasified in CO₂/N₂ mixtures containing 86, 76, 62, 40, 30, 20, 10, and 5 vol.% CO₂, with the exposure time kept sufficiently limited to neglect mass variation during the test.

Further investigation

+ H₂O/N₂ and CO₂/H₂O/N₂ atmospheres

3. Experiments

Comparison of gaseous atmospheres

- Initial pic not modified by atmosphere
- Fastest gasification using 62%CO₂+38% H₂O
- 38% H₂O 2 times faster than 40% CO₂

3. Experiments

Gasification reactions CO₂ vs H₂O

- Change of integration of CO concentration
- Change of H₂ quantity formed

Possible reactions

- Direct gasification by water:
 $C + H_2O \rightarrow CO + H_2$
- Water-gas shift reaction:
 $CO + H_2O \rightarrow CO_2 + H_2$

● 38 % H₂O ● 40 % CO₂ ● 62 % CO₂ ● 62 % CO₂ + 38 % H₂O

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2. 1D Modeling

- 2.1. Description of the thermal model – Pine pellets (LGRE) pyrolysis (100% N₂)
Results for the thermal model
- 2.2. Description of the kinetic model – Pine pellets (LGRE) pyrolysis (100% N₂)
Results for the kinetic model
- 2.3. Work in progress for gasification

2. 1D Modeling

2.1. Description of the thermal model – Pine pellets (LGRE) pyrolysis (100% N₂)

Thermal model

Heat equation

$$\rho_0 c_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = k \left(\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right) + \left(-\Delta_H \cdot \frac{dm_r}{dt} \right)$$

Boundary conditions

at the center: $\left. \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right|_{r=0} = 0$

at the surface (r = R):

$$-k \left. \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right|_{r=R} = h(T(R, t) - T_\infty) + \varepsilon \sigma (T(R, t)^4 - T_\infty^4)$$

Parameter	Value	Unit	Meaning	Source
R	0.003	m	pellet radius	measured
H	0.015	m	pellet length	
ρ_0	1230	kg m ⁻³	pellet density	calculated
c_p	1100	J kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	pellet specific heat coefficient	determined experimentally with the horizontal furnace
k	0.20	W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	pellet thermal conductivity	
T _{init}	330.15	K	initial pellet core temperature	
T _∞	873.15 973.15 1073.15 1173.15	K	target pellet core temperature	
ΔH	-2.025·10 ⁶	J kg ⁻¹	pellet heat of reaction	[12]
ε	0.90		surface emissivity	
σ	5.67·10 ⁻⁸	W m ⁻² K ⁻⁴	Stefan-Boltzmann constant	constant
h	5	W m ⁻² K ⁻¹	surface convection coefficient	
P _{atm}	101325	Pa	atmospheric pressure	constant
R _g	8.314	J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	ideal gas constant	
N	20		radial node	

[12] H.-C. Kung et A. S. Kalelkar, « On the heat of reaction in wood pyrolysis », Combustion and Flame, vol. 20, no 1, p. 91-103, févr. 1973, doi: 10.1016/S0010-2180(73)81260-X.

2. 1D Modeling

2.1. Results for the thermal model

Thermal model

2. 1D Modeling

2.2. Description of the kinetic model – Pine pellets (LGRE) pyrolysis (100% N₂)

Kinetic model for mass loss

$$\frac{dm_r}{dt} = -A \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{R_g T}\right) (m(r, t) - m_{rem}(r, t))$$

Kinetic model for the production of carbonaceous volatiles (CO₂, CO, THC)

$$m_{volatiles}(r, t) = m_{biomass\ carbon}(r, t) - (m_{residual}(r, t) + m_{char}(r, t))$$

$$\frac{dm_{volatiles}(r, t)}{dt} = - \left[A_{CO_2} e^{-\frac{E_{a,CO_2}}{(R_g T)}} + A_{CO} e^{-\frac{E_{a,CO}}{(R_g T)}} + A_{THC} e^{-\frac{E_{a,THC}}{(R_g T)}} \right] m_{volatiles}^n(r, t)$$

Work in progress:
H₂ emissions and tar production

2. 1D Modeling

2.2. Results for the kinetic model

Kinetic model for mass loss
and mass loss rate

Kinetic model for the
production of carbonaceous
volatiles (CO, CO₂, THC)

2. 1D Modeling

2.2. Results for the kinetic model

Kinetic model for the
production of carbonaceous
volatiles (CO, CO₂, THC)

Good agreement between simulations and experiments:

T (°C)	Carbon balance (%)										
	CO			CO ₂			THC			Volatiles	
	Exp.	Sim.	R ²	Exp.	Sim.	R ²	Exp.	Sim.	R ²	Exp.	Sim.
600	9.7	9.4	0.989	4.3	4.2	0.989	17.6	13.8	0.953	31.6	27.3
700	18.8	18.3	0.995	4.8	4.4	0.986	21.5	18.8	0.989	43.0	41.5
800	22.1	22.3	0.991	5.3	5.2	0.991	24.4	22.3	0.984	51.6	49.8
900	27.7	24.8	0.956	5.9	5.3	0.997	25.3	20.3	0.966	58.8	50.3

Conclusion

Conclusion

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1. Context of the study

Project presentation

